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WP06 – ACCEPT Solution integration, pre-validation, roll-out

D6.6 – Pre-Validation report of ACCEPT system in controlled environments

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable pertains to feedback received during the pre-validation activities of the various testbeds or datasets available at the time and utilized by ACCEPT partners, namely historical data from VIESGO and both the infrastructure of CERTH/ITI nZEB – DIH and Hypertech’s Office / Smart Home project and historical data from the pilot themselves, when deemed necessary. The testbeds are described in detail. After that, the assignment of the ACCEPT solution tools per testbed dataset available has taken place. The infrastructures available has proven quite adequate for all of the tools for their pre-validation. Any issues detected and their mitigation actions are reported per tool. Also, any potential deployment risks during pilot site demonstration & validation are highlighted and debugging/extensions requirement are reported. All of the tools have indicated strong performance and ready to be deployed for the demonstration activities.

Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

AMI	Advanced Metering Infrastructure
BAM	Building Asset Manager
BIML	Building Information Management Layer
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
CA	Citizen App
CERTH/ITI	Centre for Research and Technology, Hellas / Institute of Telematics and Information
DAM	District Asset Manager
DC	Direct Current
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DIML	District Information Management Layer
DR	Demand Response
DS	Distribution System
DSO	Distributed System Operator
ESCO	Energy Services Company
H-ECTs	Horizontal Energy Community Tools
HEDNO	Hellenic Distribution Network Operator
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation and Air-Conditioning
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IoT	Internet of Things
IR	Infra-Red
LCD	Liquid Crystal Display
LoRa	Long Range
ML	Machine Learning
MPP	Maximum Power Point
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
NILM	Non-Intrusive Load Monitoring
nZEB	near Zero Energy Building
P2P	Peer-to-Peer
PF	Power factor
PV	Photovoltaic
REST	Representational State Transfer
TCP/IP	Transmission Control Protocol / Internet Protocol
V-ECTs	Vertical Energy Community Tools
VPP	Virtual Power Plant
VRF	Variable Refrigerant Flow
WP	Work Package
Wp	Watt-peak
XMPP	Extensible Messaging and Presence Protocol (Also known as Jabber)

1. Introduction

1.1. Objective and Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable aims to report on the setup and operation of the small-scale benchmarking infrastructures used to support the training, experimental evaluation and validation of the ACCEPT tools developed during the WP4 and WP5 activities. Detailed description of those small-scale infrastructures or datasets used is presented, more specifically, the historical data received from VIESGO and the facilities of the Hypertech’s office/Smart Home and the CERTH/ITI nZEB – DIH testbed. Additionally, it reports on any data/equipment that has been required for the validation of the tools, debugging/extensions required and potential deployment risks that need to be highlighted and any mitigation action that has been taken, in order to be considered during the demonstration and validation activities that follows.

1.2. Interdependencies with other tasks and deliverables

Referring to pre-validation activities of the tools developed, this task and its respective deliverable, has very close ties with WP4 and WP5 activities, during which the tools are being developed. Moreover, it shares very close ties with the WP7 activities, where the main demonstration and validation activities shall take place and for which it should provide useful feedback, in order to avoid any childhood illnesses of the first integrated version of the ACCEPT solution. To that end, any feedback received from WP3 activities also can be proved useful. These interdependencies can be evidenced by the figure below.

Figure 1. Work Packages interdependencies

Furthermore, within WP6, since the activities of Task T6.4 require an initial version of the integrated ACCEPT solution, even in a preliminary state, this task is closely related to the activities of Task T6.2, in which the integration and testing of the ACCEPT solution takes place. It also serves as an input for the activities of Task T6.6, where the solution deployment, roll-out and beta-testing at the pilot premises is conducted. These interdependencies can be viewed in the figure below.

Figure 2. WP6 Tasks interdependencies

1.3. Structure of the deliverable

This deliverable is structured as follows:

- The current section, i.e. section 2, introduces the objectives and the scope of the deliverable, its structure and its relation to other tasks and deliverables,
- Section 3 presents in a detail manner the testbeds/dataset utilized for the pre-validation activities,
- Section 4 presents the tools comprising the ACCEPT solution, which testbed/dataset they have used for their pre-validation and the outcome of this process, i.e. any debugging/extension required, risk deployment etc.
- Finally, section 5 provides the conclusions of this deliverable.

2. Testbeds Controlled environments description

In this section the testbeds and any other infrastructure utilized for the pre-validation activities of the tools of the ACCEPT solution are presented, mainly:

1. the historical data provided by VIESGO,
2. the CERTH/ITI nZEB – DIH, and,
3. Hypertech's Office / Smart Home premises infrastructures.

2.1. VIESGO Historical data

The Smart Grid infrastructure setup in VIESGO provides a three-phase meter located in the secondary substation which records measurements from the medium voltage to low voltage transformer. With regards to the purpose of this project, 57 secondary substations have been selected because the meter shows overloading problems in each transformer. The data provided from those 57 meters is related to the hourly profile with a one-year historical measurements, from April 2021 to April 2022, with information regarding:

1. Supply point code for each meter
2. Serial number
3. Hourly timestamp
4. Active export per hour
5. Flag of register quality
6. Error code per hour (zero is no errors)

2.2. CERTH/ITI nZEB - DIH

The CERTH/ITI Lab operates a fully functional and well-equipped Laboratory that serves as a reference for many applications and demonstration facilities especially in the fields of sensor-based monitoring environments, simulation platform developments, big data visualization and analysis, User Modelling, Interoperable ICT, Energy and IoT applications etc.

The Smart House is a real house building where occupants can experience near-actual living scenarios. It consists of two floors and has a total area of 317.7 m², with each floor, ground and first level, having an area of 182.7 and 135 m², respectively. The entrance is on the north, north-east side for both levels, with the first floor via an external staircase. The two levels are connected within premises by a stairwell and an elevator. There is a total number of 14 rooms divided into two main categories and thermal zones.

Smart House is equipped with a vast variety of sensors, actuators, smart home devices and intelligent robots. Energy Related sensors monitor the consumption of the entire building while automated algorithms can implement building automation and/or building efficiency scenarios. In general, the Smart House is a testbed facility for innovation providers to come and test technologies with low-computing power need in Smart Home Environments.

Figure 3. CERTH Smart House

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The house and all of its equipment, including the energy generation and storage capabilities is being monitored and controlled via an IoT platform, which interfaces via Raspberry Pi gateways with the inverters and edge equipment.

Figure 4. pragma IoT platform [1] implementation for the CERTH Smart Home

2.2.1. DER Asset description

The photovoltaic panel selected is the SOLAR FRONTIER 165Wp. The number of panels used is 58, giving a total power of 9.57 kW to the system. The inverter used is the Fronius 10-kWp SYMO model with two inputs as it has two MPP Trackers. It is disconnected in the event of a power failure according to the specifications for islanding and reconnected within 180 seconds of the reset of the network, as expressly provided by HEDNO regulations.

Figure 5. PV installed on the Smart Home rooftop.

The PV system has been expanded with a battery storage system and power management system. The system harnesses the energy produced by a photovoltaic system and enables it to be stored in a dedicated lithium battery to satisfy controlled consumption. The system is an interconnected microcontroller so that the energy injection from the PV and the battery to the grid can be fully controlled.

For its implementation, three (3) single phase inverters (with built-in 70A battery chargers) were used for an autonomous system capable of operating on a microgrid. The producer of the inverter is Victron Energy, and the model is Quattro 24/3000 / 70-50 / 50. The combination of three such inverters enables real three-phase current to be used for three-phase consumption.

The inverters are also controlled through a single screen of the same company, Color Control GX, through a master / slave function, a screen compatible with TCP / IP - Modbus protocol with Ethernet and WiFi, to serve different operating scenarios. Further control and adjustment of these can be done through software included in the acquisition cost. The off-grid system can be monitored via the Victron Internet portal. Installation includes WiFi module simple for wireless interface.

As for the batteries, one (1) lithium battery of MASTERVOLT type MLI Ultra 24/5000 was used, with a total capacity of 5 kWh. This battery has its own BMS and is connected to three (3) Victron inverters / chargers.

The system was connected to the existing 10kWp power system and is located in the same area. In addition to the system board there is a relay system for isolating inverters and batteries. The systems above were set up based on communication via the Modbus protocol, as shown in the figure below.

Figure 6. CERTH Smart Home generation and storage assets communication architecture

Registry maps for each asset are available. Similar topology can be set up with SMA equipment and SUNLIGHT batteries. Since SUNLIGHT batteries support CANbus there is the possibility of direct communication with their BMS but it has not been tested at our premises. However, communication with SMA Sunny Island, with whom SUNLIGHT's BMS is (theoretically) seamlessly established, has been fully established.

The Smart House is equipped with a solar thermal flat plate collector for providing DHW, which is installed on the roof. The total area of the collector is 2.5 m² (2.0m × 1.25m). The collector is painted with selective titanium paint. The water heated by the collectors is stored in a 200 L tank. During the days of low solar radiation nZEB Smart House covers its needs for hot water through the air-to-water heat pump installation.

Figure 7. Solar thermal collector with hot water storage tank.

Furthermore, a weather Station metering system, mounted on a building's roof pole, is used to measure outdoor Climate conditions, i.e. air temperature, air relative humidity, solar radiation, wind speed and wind direction. Data are retrieved every 10 minutes.

2.2.2. Interior Asset description

The CERTH/ITI Smart House comprises of around 70kW nominal installed load, from which regular use is around 8-9kW and includes HVAC, Lighting, Home and Office Appliances.

Systems: Heating – Cooling

The HVAC system installed in Smart House is a Variable Refrigerant Flow (VRF) air conditioning system, used for both heating and cooling of the occupied spaces. Two heat pump units are installed in the building, with the first one being responsible for the heating of the ground floor, while the second one for the first floor. Both units have identical power supply characteristics: 3Φ, 380-415 V, 50 Hz.

There are two types of ceiling mounted AC terminal units, 1-Way and 4-Way Cassettes, placed at the different spaces of the building, that constitute the "demand side". Most of the models differentiate simply in the cooling and heating capacity values (while the geometry remains unchanged). The total amount of installed terminal units is 14, divided into eight units on the ground floor and six units on the first floor.

Figure 8. VRF terminal unit, 1-way cassette (left), VRF terminal unit 4-way cassette (right).

The deployment of the terminal units, the distribution system and the heat production units are presented in the figures below.

Figure 9. Smart Home HVAC – first floor plan

Figure 10. Smart Home HVAC – ground floor plan

The above-described system (heat-production, distribution, terminal units) is also utilized to cover the cooling demand of the building. Even though the system's components are identical, its behavior and operational characteristics differ in cooling mode.

Systems – Lighting

The lighting installation differs in the various spaces according to their use. At the spaces that are used as offices, the lighting requirements are more intense. For this reason, 23 lighting panels have been installed in total, on the plenums. Each panel has crosswise parabolic louvres and longwise double parabolic elements. Their shape is rectangular with dimensions 600×600×95 mm. Every device includes four LED lamps (fluorine type T8) with a power consumption of 10 W each. At the spaces with residential use (e.g., kitchen, living room, bedrooms, WCs) 43 spot lighting units in total have been installed on the plenums. Each spot is equipped with two LED lamps of 10 W each. The diameter of each spot is 230 mm and has 130 mm height. Furthermore, a linear LED lighting device is placed at the down surface of the upper cabinets of the kitchen, its power is 7 W and its dimensions are 600×250×340 mm. At the bedrooms, six wall-mounted sconce lights are installed (two in each bedroom) and each device is equipped with a 5 W LED lamp. Lastly, the emergency lighting includes four exit LED 2 W. They are equipped with Ni-Cd batteries that are capable to provide lighting for 2 hours. The total power consumption of the building’s lighting system is calculated equal to 1.95 kW (Office spaces: 0.89 kW, Residential spaces: 1.06 kW).

Figure 11. Smart Home Light fixtures.

The allocation of the lighting equipment is presented in the figures below.

Figure 12. Smart Home lightning – ground floor plan

Figure 13. Smart Home lightning – first floor plan

Meters

Smart Home utilizes electric energy as its main and only energy carrier since there is no use currently for gas or oil-fired boilers. Thus, any measuring installations refer to electricity. Electrical energy consumption is measured for the whole building, as well as for each building floor, separately. In addition, there are distinct measurements for the electrical consumption of the two existing HVAC units. The temporal granularity of the energy data available in the IoT Platform is 15 minutes. Two types of meters are utilized:

1. CARLO GAVAZZI EM270

Multi-circuit power analyzer for single or three-phase systems installable on panels or DIN rails. Manages current input via two current transformer blocks connected with RJ-11 connectors. The EM270 is equipped with a LCD display with controls to display measurements and configure the system, a RS485 port and two pulse outputs or two RS485 ports for daisy chain connections.

Figure 14. CARLO GAVAZZI EM270

2. CARLO GAVAZZI EM340

Three-phase energy meter with backlit LCD display with integrated touch keypad. Particularly indicated for active energy metering and for cost allocation in applications up to 65 A (direct connection), with dual tariff management availability. It can measure imported and exported energy or be programmed to consider only the imported one. Housing for DIN-rail mounting, with IP51 front degree protection. The meter is optionally provided with pulse output proportional to the active energy being measured, RS485 Modbus port or M-bus port. Available for legal metrology (PF option, only for imported energy).

Figure 15. CARLO GAVAZZI EM340.

Sensors

The **indoor temperature and humidity** levels throughout the building with a set of sensors (Plugwise Sense), installed in each space. It enables wireless measuring of temperature and air humidity in a room. The temperature sensor has a range of 0 to 60°C; the air-humidity sensor has a range of 5 to 95% RH. Sense is further capable of linking switch actions to certain measurement values. The collection of measurements and storage to the IoT Platform takes place periodically every 300 seconds.

Figure 16. Plugwise Sense

CO₂ sensors (Thermokon SRA04 CO₂) are used to measure carbon dioxide levels in each space. Radio room sensor for measuring CO₂ content, temperature and relative humidity (optionally) in living and office spaces. The device to be mounted via adhesive pad or screws sends its measured values unidirectionally to corresponding receivers or gateways, which process the information directly or depending on the application – forward it to a central control unit. The collection of measurements and storage to the IoT Platform take place periodically every 1000 seconds.

Figure 17. Thermokon SRA04 CO₂

The spaces' light levels are measured using dedicated **luminance sensors** (Eltako FIH65B). They are Wireless indoor brightness sensor pure white glossy for ceiling mounting, powered by a 12V DC switching power supply or with batteries. It can be screwed to any flat surface and measures brightness similar to the perception of the human eye. The collection of measurements and storage to the IoT Platform take place periodically every 100 seconds.

The infrastructure mentioned above communicates with different protocols and gateways to an IoT Platform available for real-time monitoring and control. The covered protocols are wired (BACnet, Modbus, Canbus, etc.) and wireless (ZigBee, EnOcean, Z-wave, BLE, LoRa, etc.), offering a highly diverse ecosystem for testing purposes. To support all these protocols, the IoT network is equipped with the necessary infrastructure (in the form of gateways), also allowing for easy extensions and scalability scenarios. In some cases, there are two or more alternatives for measuring similar aspects, but from different positions. The IoT Platform that collects and handles this data is also equipped with an API that offers either Restful services or event-based communication through MQTT or XMPP protocols. Currently, the communication protocol used by the IoT Platform does not follow a specific standardized approach (i.e., specific data model, sequence, etc.), but rather a custom JSON-oriented data format. However, this is something that can be adjusted if needed to facilitate integration activities. The frequency of the data originating from this highly diverse IoT ecosystem varies significantly. Some indicative examples are the electricity meters, which are from Carlo Gavazzi, and allow for a resolution of one (1) second through Modbus RTU. In contrast, for indoor conditions, one example would be the Plugwise sense that sends a measurement over ZigBee every 15 minutes (adjustable).

2.3. Hypertech's office / Smart Home premises

The Hypertech office is a fully equipped laboratory environment, which accommodates the daily business activities as an office environment at the same time. The lab is equipped with suitable devices to support the research activities in the field of IoT, flexibility profiling and demand side management. The installed equipment consists of smart cutting-edge sensing equipment, in-home displays, Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI) gateways, and smart metering/actuating devices providing a controlled environment for the functional testing and calibration of innovative services before their deployment at the pilot sites.

The premise comprises an open space of around 70m² with 9 working desks and several individual office spaces of 12m² each that accommodate 1-3 working desks, with defined thermal and visual zones and the associated sensing, control & actuation equipment. Hypertech energy labs is a living lab, which accommodates around 20 employees (acting as actual users) throughout the participation of the company in several innovative H2020 projects. The

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occupants provide voluntarily their consent and permitting the gathering of data for the validation of the Hypertech intelligence tool suite. All involved houses at the pilot sites, have been equipped with Hypertech's multi-protocol IoT Gateway to monitor their energy consumption, resident behavior and enable smart home control features. HEL Smart Home will be used to test the ACCEPT solution platform in building and community level.

Figure 18. Different aspects of Hypertech's office lab

2.3.1. DER Asset description

No DER assets are installed in the Hypertech’s office.

2.3.2. Interior Asset description

The installed IoT devices in Hypertech’s office are summarized in the table below.

Table 1: Installed IoT devices in Hypertech’s office

IoT devices installed in Hypertech’s office
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Circuit board <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ HVAC metering <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 2 x Aeotec Gen 5 Three phase smart meter ▪ 1 x Shelly-EM
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lab Small Office <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Sensing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 2x Aeotec multisensor 6 ○ Smartplugs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 1 x Aeotec smart switch 6
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lab Big Office <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Sensing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 3x Aeotec multisensor 6 ○ Smartplugs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 3 x Aeotec smart switch 6 ▪ 1x Qubino smart plug
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lab small Office 2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Sensing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 1x Aeotec multisensor 6 ○ HVAC Control <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Intesis - Fujitsu RAC and VRF systems to Home Automation Interface
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kitchen <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Smartplugs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 2 x Aeotec smart switch 6
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Openspace <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Sensing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 5 Aeotec multisensor 6) ○ Indoor Air Quality <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 1x Eurotronic Air Quality Sensor Z-Wave Plus (VOC Sensor) ▪ 1x MCO HOME MULTI-SENSOR A8-9, Z-WAVE PLUS ○ HVAC Control <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Intesis - Fujitsu RAC and VRF systems to Home Automation Interface
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other devices <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 1x Range extender ○ 1x Philips Hue Kit ○ 7 x Raspberry PI ○ 1 x Intesis IR universal controller

IoT Gateway Hardware Set-up

IoT gateway is a cheap and small-sized solution based on Raspberry Pi 4 model B, which is capable of hosting the software components of the bridge. The device provides a variety of functionalities in order to simulate a conventional PC into a computer monitor or TV, using standard keyboard, mouse and plugging. The storage capacity of the aforementioned device is increased with a 32GB SD card, and the communication with the z-wave devices is facilitated with a z-wave card. In this way, the gateway broadcasts and receives signals at a range up to 200m.

Figure 19. IoT gateway installed in Hypertech's office

Aeotec Gen 5 Three phase

This device monitors the total energy consumption of a building, by sending data to a Z-Wave gateway, in real time. In this way, the user can see how much electricity is used and when. This device is capable of communicating with Z-Wave devices up to 300ft / 90m away.

Shelly EM

The Shelly EM is a device which provides information about the quality of electricity network, regarding active power, reactive power, voltage, and power factor. This device can be used to avoid additional expense or drastic drops in energy that may damage the appliances and machines of the facility.

Aeon Labs Multisensor 6 - Z-Wave Plus

Aeon Labs Multisensor 6 - Z-Wave Plus is a multi-sensor device which has six different sensors integrated. In this way, the device monitors motion, temperature, humidity and luminance. The device is also capable of enabling the building control network to capture and interpolate the sensor's readings. For the communication of the sensor, a on Z-wave routing slave library v6.51.06 is used.

Figure 20. Aeon Labs Multisensor 6 - Z-Wave Plus installed in Hypertech's office

Qubino Smart Plug 16A

The Qubino Smart Plug is an actuator which permits the remote control of electrical devices and the real-time measurement of energy consumption. It can measure a wide variety of loads such as electric water heaters, PCs fans, lamps or microwave ovens. The device provides also backup and restore last status functionalities, auto-inclusion mode, and remote control of Z-Wave devices.

Figure 21. Qubino Smart Plug 16A installed in Hypertech's office

Aeotec Smart Switch 6

Aeotec Smart Switch 6 is a low-cost Z-Wave Switch plug-in module specifically used to enable Z-Wave command and control (on/off) of any plug-in tool. It can report immediate wattage consumption or kWh energy usage over a period of time. In the event of power failure, non-volatile memory retains all programmed information related to units operating status. Its surface has a Smart RGB LED, which can be used for indicating the output load status or strength of the wireless signal. You can configure its indication color according to your favor. The Smart Switch 6 is also a security Z-wave device and supports Over the Air (OTA) feature for the products firmware upgrade.

Eurotronic Air Quality Sensor Z-Wave Plus (VOC Sensor)

The Eurotronic Air Quality Sensor (VOC Sensor) with an ultra-slim design provides comprehensive information (temperature, humidity, VOC in ppm and CO₂) about the air quality in rooms. The information makes it possible to ensure a healthy indoor climate.

Figure 22. The Eurotronic Air Quality Sensor Z-Wave Plus (VOC Sensor) installed at Hypertech's office

MCO HOME MULTI-SENSOR A8-9, Z-WAVE PLUS

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This device is a multi-sensor which monitors the indoor air quality in terms of CO₂ levels, temperature, humidity, PM2.5, VOC, PIR, light intensity, noise. It is mainly applied to the indoor air quality measuring, learn about staff attendance situation, detect surrounding noise and lightning changes.

Figure 23: MCO HOME MULTI-SENSOR A8-9, Z-WAVE PLUS

Intesis - Fujitsu RAC and VRF systems to Home Automation Interface

The gateway is wired directly to an indoor unit. This allows not only the control of the main AC functions such as operating mode, fan speed, temperature setpoint but also the monitoring of errors and alarms. The Intesis Home Automation gateways have been specifically designed to be the best AC integration solution for Home Automation Systems. Communications are based on a simple ASCII protocol that can be easily implemented, in the form of a driver, into Home Controllers or Smart Hubs. With drivers already available from many Home Automation platforms on the market, Air Conditioning units can be easily integrated and controlled.

Figure 24. The Intesis - Fujitsu RAC and VRF systems to Home Automation Interface installed in Hypertech's office

Phillips Hue Kit

The Hue Bridge enables you to control your lights through your smartphone, voice assistants and smart accessories like motion sensors and wireless switches. It also unlocks smart features like setting schedules and routines or controlling your lights when you are away from home.

Intesis IR universal controller

The AC Cloud Control Universal IR controller allows a complete and natural integration of any IR controlled unit into AC Cloud Control system for professional HVAC control and monitoring. The gateway allows the control of the main AC functions via infrared commands. But also, thanks to the IR receiver that the device is equipped with, it is

possible to know the real status of the AC unit even the user is controlling it by the manufacturer IR remote controller.

Thermal loads

The Hypertech Lab is separated in 2 large zones, each with a dedicated heat pump for air-to-air heating and cooling. A small electric water heater is also available in the kitchen covering the daily need for hot water of the office occupants. The thermal loads of the lab are summarized in the table below.

Table 3: Installed thermal loads in Hypertech’s office

Thermal loads of Hypertech’s office		
Load type	Model type	Nominal power (kW)
Electric water heater	TESY 15 lt	1.5
2 x HVAC	Fujitsu Electric RY-45UA RO-45UA (Air-to-Air heat pump)	4.38

2.3.3. The HEL Smart Homes

As additional testbeds for the ACCEPT project, Hypertech has also used nine households in Athens and surrounding areas. The houses vary in sizes, building types, as well as with regards to the technologies installed there (for example, there are detached houses with PV systems for self-generated energy, apartments with heat pumps, etc.).

The Hypertech IoT gateway, as well as a suite of IoT devices, have been installed at all nine households for allowing the collection of data on indoor conditions, information on the usage of home appliances (loads) and available generation (in cases where the house is equipped with PVs). The gateway and IoT devices also allow Hypertech to remotely control specific domestic appliances.

The suite of IoT devices installed at the Smart Homes participating as testbeds in ACCEPT comprises, besides from the IoT gateway, of a number of measuring/metering devices, multi-sensors and controllers, and can indicatively be seen in the pictures below:

Figure 25. Qubino (DIN-rail) smart meters installed at two households (3-phase and 1-phase meters)

Figure 26. Aetoc 3-phase smart meter for total consumption measurements

Figure 27. Intesis controller for HVAC systems

Figure 28. IoT gateways and multi-sensors installed at two households

The occupants of those buildings have given their consent for testing the ACCEPT solution at their premises under the pre-validation phase, but also the retrieval of data for training some of the developed Hypertech models.

3. Models and Tools

Following the testbeds and the datasets available for use, in this section any actions pertaining to the tools of the ACCEPT solution and the pre-validation activities is presented. More specific, a short description of each, what type of data or infrastructure was used for its validation and the outcome, i.e., lessons learned from its utilization, any extensions or debugging requirements found, potential deployment risks identified and possible any mitigation actions for the later, if any. More information on the tools can be retrieved in the latest deliverable regarding the System Architecture, i.e. Deliverable D2.4 [2] .

3.1. Tools - Testbed/dataset assignment

In this section the assignment of its tool to each of the three testbeds or datasets is presented. In the ACCEPT solution arsenal there are several tools requiring a great variety of information and input, such as data from a Distribution System (DS), electricity and other energy carrier prices, weather data, indoor premises conditions etc. To that end, an assignment of these tools per testbed/dataset has been conducted. There are also tools that required data directly from the pilots, since they were available and the opportunity arose. This is presented in the table below, in a high-level manner. Since there are case of tools consisting of more than one component or even sub-components, this is presented more thoroughly in the sections that follow, where each the pre-validation activities per tool is described.

Table 1. Tool – Testbed/Dataset Assignment High-level view

Tool	VIESGO DATA (DSO/District-Level)	CERTH/ITI nZEB – DIH (Home-Level)	Hypertech’s Office/Smart Home Premises (Building/Home-Level)	Data from pilots
ACCEPT Solution emulator	X			
Citizen App		X		
Energy Community Tools	X	X	X	
P2P Exchange Platform		X	X	
Building Asset Manager		X	X	
District Asset Manager				X
Building Information layer	X	X	X	
District Information Layer				X

3.2. ACCEPT Solution Emulator

3.2.1. Description

The goal of the solution emulator is to represent the outside world. The solution requires outside communications such as Demand Response (DR) signals from a DSO and Electricity market price signals. Since these communications are not readily available or do not exist the Solution Emulator is used to fill the gap and provide the necessary external signals to demonstrate the solution.

3.2.2. Data/equipment required

In the table below the assignment of this tool and more details are presented, such as components, subcomponents, if any, any other external sources that are required for its validation and type of data that are needed. The latter is also the reason for selecting the most appropriate testbed/dataset from the ACCEPT project.

Table 2. ACCEPT Solution Emulator testbed/Dataset assignment detailed view

Tool		ACCEPT Solution Emulator	
Components		DSO Emulator	Energy Market Emulator
Technology Provider		CIRCE	
External Sources		-	Electricity Prices
Type of Data required		DSO-Level: DS data and related info	
Testbed/Dataset	from	VIESGO Historical Data	
ACCEPT Project			

3.2.3. Lessons learned

We used the data from Viesgo to model the behavior of the DSO Emulator. During testing we realized we require lower resolution data to model and test some of the electric grid congestion management services which would require more near-real-time DSO behavior and DR-requests. To fill in the gap we built a small stochastic model around the VIESGO data (which has 1h resolution) to generate DSO preferences within smaller timeframes. To properly model DSO behavior at least a year of data is required (optimally at least 2 years), and, in addition, the lack of grid infrastructure data and low resolution further limit the modelling possibilities of the emulator. For the market emulator we used open-source pricing and production indicator from the Spanish electricity market.

3.3. Citizen App

3.3.1. Description

The citizen app (CA) is a web/mobile application, inclined towards the needs of the individual citizens of the ACCEPT-project, offering several optimization, control, visualization and collaboration services that aim to integrate energy- and non-energy-services.

3.3.2. Data/equipment required

In the table below the assignment of this tool and more details are presented, such as components, subcomponents, if any, any other external sources that are required for its validation and type of data that are needed. The latter is also the reason for selecting the most appropriate testbed/dataset from the ACCEPT-project.

Table 3. Citizen App testbed/Dataset assignment detailed view

Tool		Citizen App			
Components	Building Monitoring & Control Module	Notification & Alerting System	Collaboration Forum Module	Statistical Analysis Module	Optimal Energy Schedule and Recommendation Module
Technology Provider	CERTH				
External Sources	Local Pilot Weather data, Electricity Prices				
Type of Data required	Home level: IoT Data				
Testbed/Dataset from ACCEPT Project	CERTH/ITI nZEB-DIH				

3.3.3. Lessons learned

During the pre-validation activities, any risk, unexpected condition or technical issue that was encountered and undermined the proper functionality of citizen app's deployment is mentioned in this section. The nature of the arisen issues can be divided in two categories: technical difficulties that are related with hardware inadequacy and pilot's misalignments.

The first category includes any type of communication difficulties with the premises' sensors that could lead to the interruption of the data stream supply with the required information towards the app. From the app's perspective, such types of problems can be resolved with interpolation techniques in order to fill any gap that could break the algorithmic flow and affect the inference process of the models. Additionally, any persistent sensor's malfunction needs to be spotted from the app's side, in order to be excluded from the models' requirements until the restoration of the damage. Thus, the developed algorithms (anomaly, recommendations) need to be versatile in a way that such sensors' absence could not affect the smooth operation of the app.

The second category refers to the pilot's premises misalignment with a typical household's load schedule and functionality. Despite the fact that ITI nZEB pilot disposes the required infrastructure in order to emulate a household's behaviour, there is still divergence between their load curves. Specifically, in a typical household, usually, the peak time of the energy consumption appears between 4pm and 8pm, while the pilot's consumption climaxes between 12pm and 4pm. This consumption's shifting could potentially affect the model's proper functionality as their training includes priors with regard to a general household profile. Furthermore, the level of magnitude of the loads in the pilot are much higher, while it needs to be mentioned that certain devices are not frequently used (oven).

3.4. Energy Community tools

3.4.1. Description

In this section the pre-validation activities with respect to the energy community tools are presented. The energy community tools consist of:

- the Vertical Energy Community tools (V-ECTs): those support the different roles that the energy community can assume, i.e the role of the ESCo, Retailer, and the Aggregator. These are:
 - ESCo,
 - Retailer, and,
 - Aggregator.
- The Horizontal – Energy community tools (H-ECTs): those support each of the V-ECTs to perform their functionalities These are:
 - VPP Manager,
 - Energy Community Flexibility Manager,
 - Demand Elasticity Estimator
 - P2P Supply Shadow Administrator

V-ECTs

ESCo (Hypertech)

The ESCo toolset is one of the three Vertical Energy Community tools (V-ECTs) which support the different roles that the Energy Community can assume (the role of the ESCo, the Retailer, the Aggregator). The ESCo toolset is the component responsible for the provision of compound services to the prosumers of the energy communities. For services that require the optimised operation of household appliances (such as cost optimisation, heating-as-a-service, and self-consumption), the ESCo toolset utilises the Building Information Management Layer (BIML) component, as well as (where required) the VPP Manager. There are also certain services that do not require optimisations to be performed by the ECFM, they are however performed by the ESCo toolset. For example, the continuous monitoring of the Energy Contracting KPIs for the ESCo's portfolio, as well as compound services like the Amenity-as-a-Service one.

Retailer (Hypertech/Witside)

Similar to the ESCo Toolset, the Retailer toolset performs a number of functions with the help of the H-ECTs. The Retailer Toolset is responsible for the implicit DR requests send to the prosumers of the energy community and also estimates the demand elasticity of the community's portfolio and calculates the optimal retail energy tariffs, with the help of the Demand Elasticity Estimator.

Aggregator Toolset (Hypertech)

The main role of the Aggregator Toolset is to appropriately bundle together available controllable assets under the Aggregator's portfolio to offer flexibility/DR services to third parties. In order to carry out this task, the Aggregator Toolset utilises the H-ECTs, mainly the VPP manager and the ECFM.

H-ECTs

VPP Manager (Hypertech)

The Virtual Power Plant Manager component is one of the four Horizontal Energy Community Tools (H-ECTs) and is responsible for creating, based on context provided by the Vertical Energy Community Tools (V-ECTs), suitable clusters of assets (both building- and community-level assets) under the portfolio of the Energy Community.

Energy Community Flexibility Manager (Hypertech)

The Energy Community Flexibility Manager (ECFM) is the main optimiser for the energy communities. The ECFM is triggered by the V-ECTs for the provision of specific services, such as flexibility and demand response services, cost minimisation services for the end-users, etc. Once the ECFM receives such a trigger, it solves the relevant

optimisation problem and, based on the results of this optimisation, it then dispatches demand response requests to downstream relevant assets.

Demand Elasticity Estimator (Witside)

Elasticity of demand is defined as the degree of change in demand (L) when there is a change in another economic factor, such as price (P). The Demand Elasticity Estimator is a tool developed to predict the price of electricity for the upcoming hours.

To predict the price we have used Machine Learning algorithms. More precisely, we have used an ensemble of Random Forests, XGBooster and LightGBM.

Currently, the price prediction model has been trained using publicly available data relating to the electricity consumption and prices in Spain for the time period of 2019 to 2021. The information needed to predict the price are weather data, such as temperature, radiation and precipitation, coal price and demand, both in total and demand covered by alternative resources.

P2P Supply Shadow Administrator (QUE)

The P2P Supply Shadow Administrator is the tool that organizes and stimulates the local energy trading using price signals. It provides rules and the market mechanism behind the P2P Exchange Platform in a way that guarantees the fair redistribution of revenue among the members of the community. Its functionality is closely related to the ESCo Tool since it is the tool responsible for the operation of the local exchange platform, and to the Retailer Tools as the main tool that purchases or sells energy back to the grid.

3.4.2. Data/equipment required

In the table below the assignment of this tool and more details is presented, such as components, subcomponents, if any, any other external sources that are required for its validation and type of data that are needed. The latter is also the reason for selecting the most appropriate testbed/dataset from ACCEPT project.

Table 4. Energy Community Tools testbed/Dataset assignment detailed view

Energy Community Tools							
Tool	Energy Community Tools						
Components	Retailer	ESCO	Aggregator	Horizontal Energy Community Tools			
Subcomponents	-	-	-	VPP Manager	Energy Community Flexibility Manager	Demand Elasticity Estimator	P2P Supply Shadow Administrator
Technology Provider	Hypertech/ Witside	Hypertech				Witside	QUE
External Sources	Electricity Prices	Electricity Prices				Weather data, Electricity, Crude oil, Natural Gas, Coal prices	Electricity Prices

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Type of Data required	DSO-Level: Implicit DR Requests, Demand Forecast, Historical data Building-Level: Response verification to DR-event Home-Level: Response Verification to DR-event	DSO-level: DR Requests District-Level: EV dis/charging profiles Building-Level: On-site building generation profiling Home-Level: IoT Data Flexibility Forecast	DSO-Level: Implicit DR Request Building-Level: Static Asset Information Home-Level: IoT Data	DSO-Level: Flexibility forecast request District-Level: Static/Dynamic Asset Information, Flexibility Forecasts Building-Level: Static/Dynamic Asset Information, Flexibility Forecasts Home-Level: Static/Dynamic Asset Information	DSO-Level: Flexibility forecast request District-Level: Flexibility Forecast, PV forecast, Optimization results Building-Level: Flexibility Forecast	DSO-Level: DR Request, Grid charges District-Level: Flexibility Forecasts Building-Level: Generation/Consumption Forecast	
Testbed/Dataset from ACCEPT Project	Hypertech's Office/Smart Home premises		Hypertech's Office/Smart Home premises, CERTH/ITInZEB-DIH	VIESGO Historical data	Hypertech's Office/Smart Home premises	VIESGO Historical Data	VIESGO Historical Data, Hypertech's Office/Smart Home premises, CERTH/ITInZEB-DIH

More specifically, for testing the ECFM module under the explicit DR scenario, the following data requirements applied:

- A DR request for a specific time window (in intervals of 15 minutes) and of a specific amount of energy for each timestep.
- The unique IDs of the prosumers that will participate in the DR event as provided by the VPP manager.
- Day-ahead 24-hour flexibility forecasts per asset for all the applicable prosumers.
- A compensation price for the participation of prosumers in the DR event (which is assumed to have been agreed in the relevant contract or agreement between the aggregator and the third party making the DR request).

The testing of the ECTs has been done partially. The testing of the VPP manager and some of the Vertical Tools (the ESCO and the Retailer) have not been performed to date, due to the limited scope of the tests performed and the availability of a variable enough pool of loads. Testing of these components will be performed with a pool of actual pilot users and any related information will be presented in the upcoming deliverable of the integration (Task T6.2) and deployment, roll-out and beta-testing activities (Task 6.6).

3.4.3. Lessons learned

Vertical Energy Community Tools (V-ECTs)

For the Vertical ECTs, i.e., the Retailer, Aggregator and ESCo tools, partial tests have been performed at the available testbeds. More specifically, the Aggregator toolset has been tested, acting as an intermediary tool between the DSO and the ECFM which is performing the main optimization requests on behalf of the Aggregator. No issues were faced during the testing.

VPP Manager (Hypertech)

The VPP manager has not been tested at this stage, as the implementation scenarios for testing the functionalities of the main optimizing engine for the communities of ACCEPT required the participation of all the assets at the available testbeds.

Energy Community flexibility Manager (Hypertech)

For testing the ECFM component of the ECTs, the following manual actions had to be performed:

- The cluster of prosumers included all available testbeds, i.e., the Hypertech office and the HEL smart homes. As such, the VPP manager was obsolete. The unique prosumer IDs were manually sent to the ECFM.
- The request to the ECFM was sent by the Aggregator toolset. There was no signal however received from the ASE component on this, so the request was manually generated by the Aggregator and then passed to the ECFM for carrying out the necessary optimization.

Demand Elasticity Estimator (Witside)

Since real data are not on hand, we used open-source data from the Spanish market.

The solution requires data from multiple sources. It does not only need demand data, but also weather data and gas prices.

For the sufficient training of the price prediction model, at least a year's worth of data is necessary. Until the data, and hence the model, reach maturity, results are expected to be less accurate

During the test of the component, no issues were found.

P2P Supply Shadow Administrator (QUE)

Operating a P2P trading platform is a challenging task since there is significant difference compared to a conventional energy market. The P2P Supply Shadow Administrator is the component responsible for supervising and coordinate the trading process. Therefore, extensive research was conducted to create the market mechanism that will meet the needs of the ACCEPT project. Besides the business criteria the market mechanism had to be compatible and optimized to operate on a Blockchain environment.

3.5. P2P Exchange Platform

3.5.1. Description

The P2P Exchange platform will facilitate the energy and flexibility exchange between the members of an energy community. Prosumers with a surplus of renewable energy generation will be able to trade it locally with other consumers in an environment of mutually beneficial transactions without the need a central authority. This tool will provide the means for the fair and transparent settlement of energy exchange between the members of the platform. It is based on Blockchain technology and specifically on the Tendermint¹ BFT engine and the Cosmos² Framework for maximum interoperability and security. Additionally, it has Smart Contract functionality through the Evmos³ framework, a well-tested solution for development of Smart Contracts on the Solidity⁴ programming language.

Since it is based on Blockchain technology all actors involved in transactions will be able to exchange information in an efficient, decentralized, reliable and trustworthy manner. However, the Blockchain itself can only be considered as an “advanced and secure accounting system”. The additional level of business logic and intelligence will be offered by the Smart Contracts, either in the settlement process or in the implementation of more complicated business models such as the Amenity-as-a-Service. To perform these processes the platform should exchange information with the Building Information Management Layer (BIML) and District Information Management Layer (DIML) component since it requires Metering data from the IoT infrastructure for its operation, and with the ECTs for SLAs, optimization results and pricing data to perform market operations.

3.5.2. Data/equipment required

In the table below the assignment of this tool and more details is presented, such as components, subcomponents, if any, any other external sources that are required for its validation and type of data that are needed. The latter is also the reason for selecting the most appropriate testbed/dataset from ACCEPT project.

Table 5. P2P Exchange Platform testbed/Dataset assignment detailed view

Tool		P2P Exchange Platform	
Components		Energy/Flexibility Transactions	Smart Contract Platform
Technology Provider		QUE	
External Sources		-	
Type of Data required		Home Level: IoT Data	
Testbed/Dataset	from	Hypertech’s Office/Smart Home premises, CERTH/ITI nZEB-DIH	
ACCEPT Project			

3.5.3. Lessons learned

Since it is a blockchain solution, the implementation of the P2P Exchange Platform requires for each prosumer to be an active blockchain node to ensure maximum security and trustworthiness. Blockchain nodes are the basic elements that build the infrastructure for a decentralized network. The necessary equipment requires a Linux based operational environment with a 64-bit quad-core processor and broad connectivity. Therefore, it can be hosted on the same IoT hardware that will host the rest of the BIML software components.

The solution requires metering and IoT data from the BIML and DIML components, and pricing and optimization data from ECTs.

During the tests of the component no issues were encountered.

¹ <https://tendermint.com>

² <https://v1.cosmos.network/sdk>

³ <https://evmos.org>

⁴ <https://docs.soliditylang.org/>

3.6. Building Asset Manager (BAM)

3.6.1. Description

The Building Asset Manager (BAM) is the component responsible for optimally managing building-level assets under the various scenarios implemented in ACCEPT. It comprises various sub-components, namely the on-demand flexibility manager (ODFM) and the Consumer Digital Twin (CDT). The former module is the core optimiser and control dispatch engine for all building-level assets. The latter is the module responsible for providing all necessary modelling functionalities, that concern the building, its available controllable assets and the building occupants, to the ODFM.

3.6.2. Data/equipment required

The BAM, as an integrated component, but also its sub-components were tested at the Hypertech Offices, but also at some of the Smart Homes available in Athens.

For training the required models of the CDT, namely the building thermal model, the DER models, and the thermal comfort and occupancy models⁵, the following one-month worth of data were required:

- Indoor space air temperature (every 15min)
- Outdoor air temperature (every 15min)
- Occupancy data (every 15min)
- DER power consumption (every 15min)
- DER operation status (Boolean) (every 15min)
- Setpoint temperature of the thermostat connected to control the device's operation (every 15min)
- Hourly outdoor dry bulb temperature
- Hourly global horizontal irradiance
- Hourly outdoor relative humidity
- Indoor dry bulb temperature (every 15min)
- PV system's power generation (every 15min)

Once the models of the CDT were trained, the ODFM receives the trained models from the CDT orchestrator to perform any necessary optimisations.

For the part of the testing that concerns the ODFM optimisations, the trained models from the CDT were required, as well as day-ahead weather data forecasts (with a 15-minute resolution) and day-ahead pricing data (with an hourly resolution) – the latter for performing cost-optimisations.

No partial tests were performed, as the BAM component was tested as an integrated one.

In the table below the assignment of this tool and more details are presented, such as components, subcomponents, if any, any other external sources that are required for its validation and type of data that are needed. The latter is also the reason for selecting the most appropriate testbed/dataset from ACCEPT project.

⁵ The EV profiling model has been purposely left out of the list as there are no EV chargers and EVs available at the Hypertech Offices and the HEL Smart Homes.

Table 6. Building Asset Manager (BAM) testbed/Dataset assignment detailed view

Tool			
Building Asset Manager (BAM)			
Components	On Demand Flexibility Manager	Consumer Digital Twin	
Subcomponents	-	Citizen Digital Twin	Building Digital Twin
Technology Provider	Hypertech		
External Sources	-		
Type of Data required	Building/Home Level: IoT Data		
Testbed/Dataset ACCEPT Project	from	Hypertech's Office/Smart Home premises, CERTH/ITI nZEB-DIH	

3.6.3. Lessons learned

The following issues occurred and constraints identified during the testing of the BAM under controlled conditions at the Hypertech offices and the HEL Smart Homes:

1. At the aforementioned testbeds, it has not been possible to cover all the types of loads included in the participating pilot households. For example, there are no EVs connected to the smart homes and the offices of Hypertech.
2. With regards to the Hypertech offices, the occupants of the spaces included therein, have potential different consumption and energy behaviour profiles to those of household occupants. However, the proof-of-concept testing of the BAM component (for the identification of bugs, operation problems, etc.) was completed successfully.

Other lessons learnt from the testing of the BAM component under controlled environments are the following:

3. For the sufficient training of the various CDT models, and depending on the model, at least a month's worth of data is required.
4. The installation and commissioning of appropriate IoT devices at the buildings where the solution is tested is a pre-requisite.

3.7. District Asset Manager (DAM)

3.7.1. Description

The District Assets Manager (DAM) is the component in charge of coordinating the interaction between the district assets available in the energy district and the central platform, i.e., the Energy Community tools. In particular, the DAM is composed of three main blocks:

- (i) Generation Forecasting System.
- (ii) Energy Demand Forecasting System.
- (iii) Storage Forecast/Optimisation.

3.7.2. Data/equipment required

Table 7 below reports all the data, dataset and testbed required for the DAM development.

Table 7. District Asset Manager (DAM) testbed/Dataset assignment detailed view

Tool		District Asset Manager (DAM)		
Components		Generation Forecasting Module	Storage Forecasting Module	Demand Forecasting Module
Technology Provider		CIRCE		
External Sources		Weather data, both historical and in real time		
Type of Data required		District Level: Aggregated electricity demand, District-asset-level heat demand, individual heat demand		
Testbed/Dataset from ACCEPT Project		Datasets: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Dutch, EV consumption historical data 2. Dutch, PV generation historical data 3. Swiss, PV generation historical data 4. Dutch, district heating demand historical data 5. Swiss, district heating demand historical data 		

3.7.3. Lessons learned

The PV forecasting generation is obtained from an estimation of the Global Horizontal Irradiation (GHI), which, in turn, is obtained from cloud coverage forecast. Based on a preliminary analysis, errors in the cloud coverage forecast yield a considerable source of error in forecasting the PV generation. This decision has been taken since cloud coverage forecast are available for free in on-line APIs. However, for future works, direct estimations of the GHI might be used, although at a considerable economic price.

For what is concerned with the District Heating (DH) systems, historical data available span a relatively short period of time, that is, one year and a half for the Swiss pilot and half a year for the Dutch demo. Based on a preliminary analysis, the lack of an extensive dataset for training the forecasting algorithm is actually limiting their accuracy. Secondly, not all consumers connected to the DH system are part of the ACCEPT project, so that their consumption data are not available. The absence of the bespoke data is currently limiting the possibilities of developing more effective district heating scheduling and operation.

3.8. Building Information Management Layer (BIML)

3.8.1. Description

BIML Core engine (QUE)

The BIML component is software and hardware hybrid solution responsible for the real-life and real-time information collection, processing, and storage. The hardware part consists of an IoT Gateway and a number of cloud services and tools. The Gateway acts as a bridge for the rest of the IoT infrastructure such as meters, sensors and actuators that collect the information from the prosumer premises. This architecture makes the solution scalable and flexible. It features its own security layer for preserving data integrity and enforcing information access control to other components. Data ingested from the IoT infrastructure is being processed before stored locally or sent to other components.

The physical components include the IoT Gateway, a Raspberry-pi device which hosts several software components developed to establish the seamless and secure communication between the wireless sensor network installed locally on site and the cloud-based BIML.

The Gateway collects metering and sensing IoT data from the building infrastructure and weather data from the external legacy system.

NILM tool (CERTH)

Non-Intrusive load monitoring, or NILM, tool aims at energy disaggregation, namely extracting energy consumption per appliance level. Being Non-intrusive, it requires only information extracted from energy measurements retrieved from the main switchboard of any facility, avoiding any installation of further meters within the premises. Its contribution in the ACCEPT project solution is to aid the energy community members become aware of the energy consumption at appliance level, thus, become more energy aware and leading consequently to energy efficiency. Additionally, in the DR events process, where it can aid at having more targeted and end-user-friendly DR requests.

3.8.2. Data/equipment required

In the table below the assignment of this tool and more details is presented, such as components, subcomponents, if any, any other external sources that are required for its validation and type of data that are needed. The latter is also the reason for selecting the most appropriate testbed/dataset from ACCEPT project.

Table 8. Building Information Management Layer (BIML) testbed/Dataset assignment detailed view

Tool		Building Information Management Layer (BIML)	
Components		Core Engine	NILM
Technology Provider		QUE	CERTH
External Sources		-	
Type of Data required		Home Level: IoT Data (Energy metering)	
Testbed/Dataset	from	Hypertech’s Office/Smart Home premises, CERTH/ITI nZEB-DIH	
ACCEPT Project			

3.8.3. Lessons learned

BIML Core engine (QUE)

The BIML Core engine offers seamless integration for a number of cloud-based tools. The most important lessons were taken in the fields of scalability and interoperability. The first one since it allows the integration of numerous devices while ensuring uninterrupted and error-free operation. And the second to allow a wide range of communication protocols to coexist and evolve in parallel.

NILM tool (CERTH)

The implementation of disaggregation algorithms in ITI Smarthome facilities has contributed towards gaining the necessary experience for successfully setting up NILM systems in pilot sites. Data completeness and proper storage is a primary factor that should be taken into consideration. Missing data could severely affect the algorithm's performance since each appliance's signature requires fine grained details in order to be distinguished from the aggregated consumption. Data filling methods can be applied in certain cases, however when large chunks of data are missing, the missing information practically can't be restored. Moreover, it needs to be highlighted that the training process requires the provision of synchronized data from both the appliances and the total consumption. Data sampling frequency is also of utmost importance. It has been empirically found that at least one measurement per minute is required in order to achieve a decent level of accuracy for most of the appliances. Another factor that defines the level of accuracy is related to the variable that is being sub-metered and disaggregated. Power measurements are less accurate since they only represent the instant rate of energy transfer while energy describes the total amount of energy that was consumed from the appliance within the timeframe of the sampling period. The evaluation of the ML algorithms is also important and should give a complete and unbiased picture regarding the performance of the models. This is accomplished by utilizing both classification and regression metrics during the evaluation process, aiming to capture the operational status (on/ off) of the appliances and the exact amount of energy that was consumed, respectively. Finally, scaling issues should be considered when it is attempted to deploy pilot sites on a large scale. The option of local storage and deployment of the models on edge appliances could be studied, so as to avoid the disadvantages (storage requirements, training time) of deploying the whole service from a central server.

3.9. District Information Management Layer (DIML)

3.9.1. Description

The DIML component is responsible for managing the district level components of the solution. It was conceived as an IoT gateway and tool bundle responsible for the communications and low level management of the district services.

3.9.2. Data/equipment required

In the table below the assignment of this tool and more details are presented, such as components, subcomponents, if any, any other external sources that are required for its validation and type of data that are needed. The latter is also the reason for selecting the most appropriate testbed/dataset from ACCEPT project.

Table 9. District Information Management Layer (BIML) testbed/Dataset assignment detailed view

Tool		District Information Management Layer (DIML)
Components		-
Technology Provider		CIRCE
External Sources		-
Type of Data required		District Level:
Testbed/Dataset	from	Data from pilots
ACCEPT Project		

3.9.3. Lessons learned

During the project we discovered that all the systems from the pilots we already managed and that installing a new IoT gateway would be an unacceptable disruption to the systems already on place in the pilots. Due to this an alternate approach was taken where the DIML acts as a virtual IoT gateway communicating remotely with the systems already in place on the pilot sites. The DIML communicates with the pilot SCADA systems and translates those signals to the project's needs.

During roll out we also discovered that the EV chargers at the Dutch pilot were not manageable, we are searching for a new EV charger to be integrated into the DIML as it is necessary for some use cases.

In the case of the AEM pilot site final communications are yet to be completed. To mitigate this a mock up device was create to serve IoT data coming from the AEM pilot.

It is not uncommon for district level devices to have SCADA/management systems already in place in which case deploying a new IoT gateway device might not be feasible. In these cases the approach of creating a virtual component managing communications with the systems already in place might be the most practical solution.

4. Conclusions

This deliverable pertains to feedback received during the pre-validation activities of the various testbeds or datasets available at the time and utilized by ACCEPT partners, namely historical data from VIESGO and both the infrastructure of CERTH/ITI nZEB – DIH and Hypertech’s Office / Smart Home project and historical data from the pilot themselves, when deemed necessary. The testbeds are described in detail. After that, the assignment of the ACCEPT solution tools per testbed dataset available has taken place. The infrastructures available has proven quite adequate for all of the tools for their pre-validation. Any issues detected and their mitigation actions are reported per tool. Also, any potential deployment risks during pilot site demonstration & validation are highlighted and debugging/extensions requirement are reported. All of the tools have indicated strong performance and ready to be deployed for the demonstration activities.

5. References

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